

Does incongruence between civil servants' and citizens' socioeconomic status negatively affect how citizens relate to civil servants and local governments?

A vignette survey experiment

ODISSEI-LISS Research Proposal

Dr. Vivian Visser, prof. dr. Willem de Koster and prof. dr. Jeroen van der Waal

1. Layperson summary (1689w)

Inspired by the literature on 'diploma democracies', indicating that the overrepresentation of higher socioeconomic status (SES) politicians reduces lower SES citizens' political trust and voter turn-out, we want to study the effect of **civil servants' SES** background on how citizens relate to both civil servants and local governments. Given that today's bureaucratic organizations are dominated by higher SES professionals, we use a pre-registered population-based vignette survey experiment to test whether **(in)congruence** between civil servants' and citizens' SES affects how citizens relate to civil servants and local governments. We expect that when there is a congruence between civil servants' and citizens' SES, citizens a) perceive more cultural proximity between themselves and civil servants, b) have more trust in civil servants and the local government, and c) are more willing to participate with civil servants and the local government. Our study therewith crucially advances our understanding of democratic (non-)participation, and provides a starting point for tackling the unwanted underrepresentation in all forms of participatory democracy of citizens with a lower SES.

2. Background of the study and relation to the literature (661w)

Western European citizens live in '**diploma democracies**', in which politicians from high social status backgrounds are strongly overrepresented (Bovens & Wille, 2017). Scholars pay considerable attention to the consequences thereof for how citizens relate to governments. This literature shows that especially citizens with a lower SES do not feel represented in the democratic system (Bovens & Wille, 2017) and experience a cultural distance between themselves and politicians (Noordzij, de Koster & van der Waal, 2021) which results in low voter turn-out and little political trust among these groups.

Such attention to the status of office holders would not only benefit our understanding of how citizens relate to politics, but also of citizens' relation to civil servants and local government. Local governments nowadays experiment with **participatory schemes** to involve citizens in public decision-making processes (Elstub & Escobar, 2019).¹ These attempts to 'bridge the gap' between governments and citizens have, so far, fall short in attracting all citizens equally. It appears that especially citizens with a **lower SES are underrepresented** in all forms of participatory democracy (Dekker & Uslaner, 2001; Stolle & Hooghe, 2011; Tonkens & Verhoeven, 2019). Both scholars and pundits warn that increasing opportunities for citizen participation might negatively affect groups that do not participate and therewith increase social inequalities (Fung, 2006; Newman & Tonkens, 2011).

Existing research aiming to understand social inequalities in participation predominantly focuses on the background **characteristics of citizens** that stimulate or hamper their participation, like time, money and political knowledge (Dekker & Uslaner, 2001; Galston, 2001, Verba, Nie & Kim, 1979). However, recent studies indicate that the **characteristics of civil servants** might also influence citizens' willingness to participate. We have ourselves recently uncovered in an in-depth, qualitative study that **lower SES citizens** experience a **distance between themselves and civil servants**, whom they see as coming from a **higher SES background than themselves**, which hinders them to participate (Visser, de Koster & van der Waal, 2022). Informed by these findings, our **novel theory** in this proposed study,

¹ This is often organized at the neighbourhood level (Tonkens & Verhoeven, 2019). Citizens are then, for example, invited to think along in redesigning the public space in their neighbourhood or to develop a neighbourhood agenda that identifies the issues that matter most to citizens.

does not focus on the background characteristics of citizens alone, but on the **(in)congruence** between the backgrounds of civil servants and citizens instead, to explain how citizens relate to civil servants and local governments.

Literature on **representative bureaucracy** – i.e. an administrative workforce that reflects the demography of the population – in for example education, law enforcement and regulatory agencies, suggests that the background of civil servants plays an important role in how different groups of citizens are served. Recently, Riccucci and Van Ryzin (2017) argued that through **symbolic representation** the background of civil servants matters in such a way that when civil servants represent the social identity of citizens - i.e. when there is **congruence** between citizens' and civil servants' social identity - this **enhances citizens' trust and increases their willingness to cooperate** with the government.

To date, representative bureaucracy research has focussed on the role of race and gender (Vinopal, 2020), and has been primarily conducted in the United States. We are the **first to test the effect of civil servants' SES** in the European context, where political and civic attitudes and behaviours are most strongly divided along SES lines (Dekker & Uslaner, 2001; Tonkens & Verhoeven, 2019). We aim to test the effect of civil servants' SES of origin on how citizens relate to them and the local government in the strategic context of the Netherlands, which is characterized by an outspoken socio-economic gradient in citizens' participation (Dekker, 2019). Given significant and persistent differences in lifestyles, preferences and values between lower and higher SES groups – originating in socialisation processes within the milieu of their childhood (Lareau, 2003) – we theorize that symbolic representation of SES influences how citizens relate to civil servants and the local government.

3. Research question and conceptual model (109w)

We aim to answer the following research question:

Does (in)congruence between civil servants' and citizens' socioeconomic status shape how citizens relate to civil servants and local governments?

We expect that **when civil servants and citizens share their SES**, citizens a) perceive **more cultural proximity** between themselves and civil servants (cf. Noordzij, de Koster & van der Waal, 2021), b) have **more trust** in civil servants and the local government (cf. Noordzij, de Koster & van der Waal, 2020; Theobald & Haider-Markel, 2009) c) are **more willing to participate** with civil servants and the local government (Riccucci, van Ryzin & Li, 2016; Visser, de Koster & van der Waal, 2021).

4. Methodological approach (955w)

Experimental design

We will use a **pre-registered population-based survey experiment**, with high internal and external validity (Mutz, 2011) – and have ample experience in that regard (i.a., Lindner et al., 2023; Mijs, de Koster & van der Waal, 2021; Noordzij, de Koster & van der Waal, 2023; Van den Hoogen, de Koster & van der Waal, 2023; Van Meurs et al., 2022). Respondent will be randomly assigned to 1 out of 2 vignettes, after which they will answer to 15 Likert items and an attention check. In our experiment, a **civil servant will**

introduce himself² via a newsletter (b1-language level) as the respondents' new neighborhood manager. The civil servant expresses the wish to meet residents, to learn about the neighborhood and issues that matter to citizens. When introducing himself, the civil servant will tell a bit about his **personal and professional background**, which we will **experimentally vary**. We vary well-known SES of origin 'cues' – occupation of the parent(s), study and career path, and leisure activity (Noordzij, de Koster & van der Waal, 2023; Raaphorst, 2017) – to signal whether the civil servant has a high or low SES of origin (see section 6 below). Thanks to the first author's **extensive first-hand experience** in governmental organizations, we are able to design vignettes that resemble **real life governmental newsletters and profiles from civil servants**, therewith securing external validity. An AI-generated picture of the civil servant will be embedded in the vignette to further increase the realistic quality of the vignette.

Sample and timing

We intend to use the standard **sample of 2500 respondents**. Reading the vignette and answering our small number of questions (see section 6 below) **will not exceed the 15-minute** time limit. Since we are interested in a form of political participation, our sample must be **representative for the Dutch population**, from the age of 18 and above. We have no specific constraints regarding the timing of our study, but prefer to collect the data as soon as possible.

Independent variable

We are interested in the effects of the (in)congruence between civil servants' and citizens' SES on citizens' relation with civil servants and local governments. Our **vignettes** (see section 6 below) are designed to measure the SES of origin of civil servants and serve as independent variables in our study.

Outcome variables

We use validated scales for our outcomes of interest. '**Perceived cultural proximity**' (cf. Noordzij, de Koster & van der Waal, 2021) is measured with 5 statements, with answer categories ranging from (1) completely disagree to (7) completely agree (that will be reversely recoded): *most civil servants* (a) ... *are far removed from people like me*; (b) ... *do not know what is going on for people like me*; (c) ... *live lives completely different from those of people like me*; (d) ... *want to impose their way of life on people like me*; and (e) ... *look down on people like me*.

Trust in the civil servant and local government are measured with questions based on the widely used single item question to measure political trust: On a scale from 0 to 10, can you indicate how much trust you personally have in: (a) *the civil servant introduced in the flyer you have just read*; (b) *the local government*. Additionally, we will measure trust in the civil servant using items inspired by a recently developed and validated multi-dimensional measurement of (political) trust, taking into account the dimensions of competence, care, accountability and reliability (Noordzij, de Koster & van der Waal, 2023). This will be measured using the following items, with answer categories ranging from (1) completely disagree to (7) completely agree: *This civil servant* (a) ... *is able to solve problems*; (b) ... *achieves what he wants to achieve*; (c) ... *cares about what's important to me*; (d) ... *listens to criticism*; and (e) ... *does what he says*.

Intention to participate is measured with 3 statements, with a 5-point answer range from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree' (Lin, 2006): (a) *I am willing to cooperate with this civil servant*; (b) *I plan to cooperate with this civil servant*; and (c) *I will make an effort to cooperate with this civil servant*.

Variables used to measure citizens' SES

Following the literature, educational level is the most important SES indicator explaining differences in political attitudes and behavior in the Netherlands (Noordzij, de Koster & van der Waal, 2021). Therefore, we use **educational level** of respondents, available in the background data of the LISS panel as 'highest level of education with diploma', to formally *test* our hypotheses. In addition, we *explore* the effect of other relevant indicators commonly used for measuring SES, therewith making the **most use of existing LISS**

² For the low SES civil servant, we want to describe a credible career path, from physical laborer to neighborhood manager. Given that physical labor is gendered (Connell, 2006), we have opted for a male civil servant, to ensure the external validity of our vignettes.

panel data. We use respondent's indication of total monthly household income after taxes to measure **income**. We use answers to the question 'can you indicate, on a scale from 0 to 10, how hard or how easy it is for you to live off the income of your household' to measure respondents' **difficulty to make ends meet** (LISS core study Income). **Perceived social position** is measured with the questions 'where do you put yourself on this ladder' and 'and if you think about the family you grew up in, where would you place it on that ladder' (ISSP 2015 – Work orientations). Since we use **existing LISS panel data** and merge these with our new data, we have the major advantage that we **do not prime respondents** in our experiment (Druckman & Leeper, 2012).

5. Implications for research, practice and/or society (321w)

Our project is highly relevant for research, practice and society. The project **advances social-scientific understanding** of differences in willingness to participate in democratic innovations among different social groups. It does so by testing a **novel theory** that focuses on the (in)congruence between the SES of civil servants and citizens. Inspired by research in the US, we are the first to test the mechanism of symbolic representation of SES and with a focus on Europe. This study will add a **crucial element** to the current research project of the first author, in which she uses various qualitative methods to study in-depth how local governments can tailor participatory processes to different social groups of citizens. The proposed study will enable her to accomplish the **full empirical research cycle** from inductive, qualitative theory development to deductive, quantitative testing of that novel theory in a national representative sample.

Our project provides **policy makers and other civil servants** crucial insights on how to deal with the issue of social inequalities in citizen participation; an issue high on their agenda (e.g. Tonkens & Verhoeven, 2019). Current attempts to tackle inequalities in participation focus on reducing practical barriers to participate and 'empowerment' of lower SES citizens (Ianniello et al., 2018). If our hypotheses are corroborated, our study would provide the first and clear indication that governmental organizations should not focus on these measures alone, but also **strive for a more diverse workforce** that is representative of the population. Therewith, our study has the potential to provide inspiration for **new courses of action** to reduce inequality in participation.

In addition, our study contributes to **societal debates** on citizen participation, in which those not participating citizens are often erroneously depicted as 'simply not interested' in public matters (Manning & Holmes, 2013; Visser, de Koster & van der Waal, 2022). By focusing on the effect of characteristics of civil servants, our study could provide a **more nuanced** understanding of this phenomenon.

Output

- Article in a highly ranked disciplinary journal as *Public Administration Review* or *Public Administration*, aiding the first author to write a strong NWO VENI-application
- Informing public officials who are concerned with citizen participation via e.g., Kennisknooppunt Participatie of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water and Gemeente Rotterdam (partners we already collaborate with)
- Publication on well-read online platforms *Sociale Vraagstukken* and *PlatformO* for policy officers and others interested in local governments and citizen participation.

6. Preliminary survey

Intro

Deze vragenlijst begint met een brief van de gemeente. Op het volgende scherm ziet u de brief. **Het is belangrijk dat u de brief goed leest.**

Randomly assigned vignette

Low SES civil servant:

Beste bewoner,

Nieuwe wijkmanager

Ik ben Harm Smit. Ik ben uw nieuwe wijkmanager. Als wijkmanager kijk ik wat er in de wijk speelt. En wat er moet gebeuren om de wijk te verbeteren. Dat bepaal ik samen met bewoners. Ik zet mij graag in zodat het in uw wijk plezierig wonen en leven is.

U kunt bij mij terecht

Wilt u iets leuks organiseren voor uw buurt of straat? Of heeft u vragen over uw wijk of de gemeente? Dan kunt u bij mij terecht.

Ik spreek graag met u

Ik spreek graag met u en andere bewoners. Dan kan ik horen welke onderwerpen voor u belangrijk zijn. En welke ideeën u heeft over het verbeteren van uw wijk. Binnenkort bel ik daarom bij u aan. Gaat u met mij in gesprek? Ik hoop het!

Met vriendelijke groet,

Harm

Even voorstellen...

Ik ben een enthousiaste wijkmanager die graag problemen oplost. Mijn vader werkte als postbode. Net als hij, zit ik niet graag stil achter een bureau. Dus ben ik na mijn middelbare school direct lekker met mijn handen gaan werken. Ik begon bij de gemeente als medewerker groenonderhoud. Ik vond het heerlijk om buiten te zijn, struiken te snoeien, bloemen te planten en afval te verwijderen. Nu zet ik me in voor de buurt in mijn rol als wijkmanager. In mijn vrije tijd kunt u me tegenkomen bij het water. Vissen is mijn grote hobby.

High SES civil servant:

Beste bewoner,

Nieuwe wijkmanager

Ik ben Floris van Duyvenvoorde. Ik ben uw nieuwe wijkmanager. Als wijkmanager kijk ik wat er in de wijk speelt. En wat er moet gebeuren om de wijk te verbeteren. Dat bepaal ik samen met bewoners. Ik zet mij graag in zodat het in uw wijk plezierig wonen en leven is.

U kunt bij mij terecht

Wilt u iets leuks organiseren voor uw buurt of straat? Of heeft u vragen over uw wijk of de gemeente? Dan kunt u bij mij terecht.

Ik spreek graag met u

Ik spreek graag met u en andere bewoners. Dan kan ik horen welke onderwerpen voor u belangrijk zijn. En welke ideeën u heeft over het verbeteren van uw wijk. Binnenkort bel ik daarom bij u aan. Gaat u met mij in gesprek? Ik hoop het!

Met vriendelijke groet,

Floris

Even voorstellen...

Ik ben een enthousiaste wijkmanager die graag problemen oplost. Mijn vader werkte als burgemeester. Tijdens mijn studie Bestuurskunde was ik voorzitter van het studentencorps. Via meerdere commissies zette ik mij in voor anderen. Ik kwam erachter dat ik graag een positieve bijdrage wil leveren aan de samenleving. Dat deed ik daarna in verschillende functies bij de Rijksoverheid. En nu dus in mijn nieuwe functie als wijkmanager. In mijn vrije tijd ga ik graag naar het theater of kunt u me vinden op het hockeyveld.

Questions

De volgende vragen gaan over de brief die u net gelezen hebt.

1) Perceived cultural proximity

In hoeverre bent u het oneens of eens met de volgende uitspraken?

De ambtenaar die zich voorstelt in de brief...

- ... staat ver af van mensen zoals ik
- ... weet niet wat er leeft bij mensen zoals ik
- ... leidt een heel ander leven dan mensen zoals ik
- ... wil zijn manier van leven opdringen aan mensen zoals ik
- ... kijkt neer op mensen zoals ik

2) Trust in the civil servant and local government:

In hoeverre bent u het oneens of eens met de volgende uitspraken?

De ambtenaar die zich voorstelt in de brief...

- ... is in staat om problemen op te lossen
- ... bereikt wat hij wil bereiken

- ... zorgt voor wat belangrijk voor mij is
- ... luistert naar kritiek
- ... doet wat hij zegt

Kunt u op een schaal van 1 tot 10 aangeven hoeveel **vertrouwen** u persoonlijk hebt in ...

- ... de ambtenaar die zich voorstelt in de brief die u net gelezen hebt
- ... uw gemeente

3) Willingness to participate:

In hoeverre bent u het oneens of eens met de volgende uitspraken?

- Ik **wil** met deze ambtenaar in gesprek gaan om de wijk te verbeteren
- Ik **ben van plan** met deze ambtenaar in gesprek te gaan om de wijk te verbeteren
- Ik **zal mijn best doen** om met deze ambtenaar in gesprek te gaan om de wijk te verbeteren

For questions 1-3, possible answers are on a 7-point range, from ‘strongly disagree’ to ‘strongly agree’: (1) helemaal oneens (2) oneens (3) een beetje oneens (4) niet oneens en niet eens (5) een beetje eens (6) eens (7) helemaal eens.

Treatment-relevant attention check

De volgende vraag gaat over de brief die u gelezen hebt. Wees in uw antwoord zo precies mogelijk. Als u het antwoord niet weet, is dat geen probleem. U kunt dat aangeven met de keuze “weet ik niet”

- 4) Waar ging de brief van de gemeente over?
 - a) De brief stelde de wijkmanager voor
 - b) De brief ging over verhoging van de belasting door de gemeente
 - c) De brief kondigde aan dat de riolering in de straat vervangen wordt
 - d) Weet ik niet

Debriefing

De brief van de gemeente die u aan het begin van de vragenlijst zag, is door **de onderzoekers** verzonden. De brief is niet verstuurd door uw gemeente.

Met dit onderzoek wordt bestudeerd of eigenschappen van ambtenaren invloed hebben op hoe mensen denken over de gemeente, en of zij daardoor meer of minder bereid zijn samen te werken met ambtenaren.

7. Existing LISS panel data used

Variable	Variable name in LISS data	Description codebook
Education	Oplmet	Highest level of education with diploma 1 Primary school 2 Vmbo (intermediate secondary education, US: junior high school)

		<p>3 Havo/vwo (higher secondary education/preparatory university education, US: senior high school)</p> <p>4 Mbo (intermediate vocational education, US: junior college)</p> <p>5 Hbo (higher vocational education, US: college)</p> <p>6 Wo (university)</p> <p>7 Other</p> <p>8 Not (yet) completed any education</p> <p>9 Not yet started any education</p>
Income	Nettohh_f	Net household income in Euro
Difficulty to make ends meet	ci220378	Can you indicate, on a scale from 0 to 10, how hard or how easy it is for you to live off the income of your household? 0 means that it is very hard to live off your income, 10 means that it is very easy.
Perceived social position	nk16a145 nk16a146	<p>There are groups that are at the top of our society, but there are also groups that are located almost at the bottom. Here you see a ladder with ten steps. Where do you put yourself on this ladder?</p> <p>And if you think about the family you grew up in, where would you place it on that ladder?</p> <p>1 means bottom, 10 means top.</p>

References

- Bovens, M. & Wille, A. (2017). *Diploma Democracy: The Rise of Political Meritocracy*. Oxford University Press
- Connell, R. (2006). Glass Ceilings or Gendered Institutions? Mapping the Gender Regimes of Public Sector Worksites. *Public Administration Review*, 66(6), 837–849.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/4096601>.
- Dekker, P. (2019). From pillarized active membership to populist active citizenship: The Dutch do-democracy. *Voluntas*, 30, 74-85. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11266-018-00058-4>.
- Dekker, P. & Uslander, E.M. (2001). *Social Capital and Participation in Everyday Life*. Routledge.
- Druckman, J.N. & Leeper, T.J. (2012). Learning more from political communication experiments: Pretreatment and its effects. *American Journal of Political Science*, 56(4), 875-896.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5907.2012.00582.x>.
- Elstub, S. & Escobar, O. (2019). *Handbook of democratic innovation and governance*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Fung, A. (2004). *Empowered participation: Reinventing urban democracy*. Princeton University Press.
- Galston, W.A. (2001). Political knowledge, political engagement, and civic education. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 4, 217–234.
- Ianniello, M., Iacuzzi, S., Fedele, P., & Brusati, L. (2019). Obstacles and solutions on the ladder of citizen participation: a systematic review. *Public management review*, 21(1), 21-46.
- Lareau, A. (2003) *Unequal childhoods: Class, race, and family life*. University of California Press.
- Lin, H. (2006). Understanding behavioural intention to participate in virtual communities. *CyberPsychology & Behaviors*, 9(5), 540-547. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cpb.2006.9.540>.
- Lindner, T., Mijs, J., de Koster, W. & van der Waal, J. (2023). Does Informing Citizens about the Non-Meritocratic Nature of Inequality Bolster Support for a Universal Basic Income? Evidence from a Population-Based Survey Experiment. *European Societies*.
- Manning, N. & Holmes, M. (2013). “He’s snooty ‘im”: Exploring ‘white working class’ political disengagement. *Citizenship Studies*, 17(3–4), 479–490.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13621025.2013.793082>.

- Mijs, J., de Koster, W. & van der Waal, J. (2021). Belief Change in Times of Crisis: Providing Facts about COVID-19-Induced Inequalities Closes the Partisan Divide but Fuels Republican Intra-Partisan Polarization about Inequality. *Social Science Research* 104: 102692.
- Mutz, D.C. (2011). *Population-based survey experiments*. Princeton University Press.
- Newman, J. & Tonkens, E. (2011). *Participation, responsibility and choice*. Amsterdam University Press.
- Noordzij, K., De Koster, W. & Van der Waal, J. (2020). “They don’t know what it’s like to be at the bottom”: Exploring the role of perceived cultural distance in less-educated citizens’ discontent with politicians. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 72(3), 566-579. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-4446.12800>.
- Noordzij, K., De Koster, W. & Van der Waal, J. (2021). A revolt of the deplored? The role of perceived cultural distance in the educational gradient in anti-establishment politics. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 72(5), 1448-1463. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-4446.12892>.
- Noordzij, K., De Koster, W. & Van der Waal, J. (2023). Explaining the educational gradient in trust in politicians: a video-vignette survey experiment. *West European Politics*. Online first: DOI: [10.1080/01402382.2023.2250163](https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2023.2250163)
- Raaphorst, N.J. (2017). *Uncertainty in bureaucracy: Toward a sociological understanding of frontline decision making*. Erasmus University Rotterdam.
- Riccucci, N. M., & Van Ryzin, G. G. (2017). Representative bureaucracy: A lever to enhance social equity, coproduction, and democracy. *Public Administration Review*, 77(1), 21-30.
- Riccucci, N. M., Van Ryzin, G. G., & Li, H. (2016). Representative bureaucracy and the willingness to coproduce: An experimental study. *Public Administration Review*, 76(1), 121-130.
- Stolle, D. & Hooghe, M. (2010). Shifting inequalities. Patterns of exclusion and inclusion in emerging forms of political participation. *European Societies*, 13(1), 119-142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616696.2010.523476>.
- Theobald, N. & Haider-Markel, D. (2009). Race, Bureaucracy, and Symbolic Representation: Interactions between Citizens and Police. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 19(2), 409 – 26.
- Tonkens, E., & Verhoeven, I. (2019). The civic support paradox: Fighting unequal participation in deprived neighbourhoods. *Urban Studies*, 56(8), 1595-1610.
- Van den Hoogen, E., de Koster, W. & van der Waal, J. (2023). Does the prospect of further sovereignty loss fuel Euroscepticism? A population-based survey experiment. *European Societies*.
- Van Meurs, T., de Koster, W., van der Waal, J. & Oude Groeniger, J. (2022). Receptive to an Authoritative Voice? Experimental Evidence on How Patronizing Language and Stressing Institutional Sources Affect Public Receptivity to Nutrition Information. *SSM Population Health* 20: 101295.
- Verba, S., Nie, N. and Kim, J. (1979). *Participation and political equality: A seven nation comparison*. Cambridge University Press.
- Vinopal, K. (2020). Socioeconomic representation: Expanding the theory of representative bureaucracy. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 30(2), 187-201.
- Visser, V., De Koster, W., & Van der Waal, J. (2022). Understanding less-educated citizens’ (non-)participation in citizens’ initiatives: Feelings of entitlement and a taste for politics. *Current Sociology*, 71(5), 924-942.